

Klein et al. study shows HPV vaccine is associated with type 1 diabetes as expected from mechanistic evidence but the authors misinterpret the statistics to come to the wrong conclusion

Vinu Arumugham

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vinucubeacc@gmail.com

Klein et al. (1) conclude that the HPV vaccine is not associated with type 1 diabetes.

They calculate a hazard ratio of 1.21, 95% Confidence Interval (CI) 0.94, 1.57. They wrongly conclude that there is no association because the 95% CI covers HR=1.0. As described before, such a significance testing based conclusion is wrong (2).

We have strong mechanistic evidence that yeast, animal and plant protein containing vaccines do cause type 1 diabetes (3–6). The HPV vaccines contain yeast, animal (insect) (7) and plant proteins (8).

Please see more details regarding safety problems associated with yeast in vaccines in my comment published in the Annals of Internal Medicine:

Yeast proteins in HBV (and HPV) vaccines are a fundamental safety flaw

<https://annals.org/aim/fullarticle/2664089/hepatitis-b-vaccination-screening-linkage-care-best-practice-advice-from>

Please see more details as to why epidemiological studies are broken, in my comments published in the Annals of Internal Medicine:

MMR and autism study is fundamentally flawed

and

Authors' inability to address vaccine content variation effect and lack of control for multiple mechanisms is very troubling

<https://annals.org/aim/fullarticle/2727726/measles-mumps-rubella-vaccination-autism-nationwide-cohort-study>

Epidemiological studies are not only useless, they maim and mislead

The US Institute of Medicine committee in their 2011 report (9) on Adverse Effects of Vaccines: Evidence and Causality wrote:

"The committee concluded the evidence convincingly supports 14 specific vaccine–adverse event relationships. In all but one of these relationships, the conclusion was based on strong mechanistic evidence with the epidemiologic evidence rated as either limited confidence or insufficient."

So in an overwhelming 93% (13 of 14) cases, mechanistic studies provided convincing evidence and epidemiological studies failed to do so. Epidemiological studies are weak, have numerous sources of confounding and offer little value. Epidemiological study results are misinterpreted leading to type II errors. (2) Basically, with all vaccines containing uncontrolled levels of numerous non-target proteins (food, animal, fungal, viral/bacterial, etc), epidemiological studies are useless. The results cannot be replicated. These studies are ripe for cherry-picking. Do you want to claim the rotavirus vaccine is **associated** with type 1 diabetes (10)? Do you want to claim the rotavirus vaccine **protects** against type 1 diabetes (11)? Take your pick.

Klein et al. is the latest example of a failed epidemiological vaccine safety study that spreads the myth of vaccine safety.

All the while, case reports of autoimmune diseases following vaccines in general and the HPV vaccine in particular, are piling up (12), consistent with reliable mechanistic evidence.

References

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